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ZJAWISKO SPOŁECZNO-KULTURALNE ZACHOWANIA ZDROWIA I JEGO MIEJSCE W SYSTEMIE KATEGORII PEDAGOGICZNYCH

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Streszczenie. Na podstawie analizy i uogólnienia szeregu badań naukowych autor uzasadnia pilność podniesionego problemu, dokonał teoretycznej eksploracji jego istoty; podkreślił, że zdrowie jest zjawiskiem społeczno-kulturowym; podstawowe cechy podstawowych definicji, ich geneza, sposoby formowania się w aspekcie określonego kierunku i ich miejsce w systemie kategorii pedagogicznych jako ważna koncepcja pojęcia edukacji, dynamicznej, całościowej formacji, przejawiająca się na różnych poziomach życia: somatyczne, mentalne, moralne, duchowe.

Istnieje wiele pojęć, które określają podstawową podstawę badania, w tym „zdrowie”, „oszczędzanie zdrowia”, „kultura oszczędzania zdrowia”, „promocja zdrowia” („promocja zdrowia”); podstawowe aspekty opieki zdrowotnej zostały przeanalizowane.

Stwierdzono, że cechy semantyczne podstawowych pojęć problemu oszczędzania zdrowia z powodzeniem wprowadzono do systemu kategorii pedagogicznych; analizowane koncepcje są szeroko stosowane w teorii i praktyce pedagogicznej, reprezentując istotę podstawowych procesów związanych z zachowaniem, wzmocnieniem i powstawaniem badanego zjawiska.

Scharakteryzowano naukowe i pedagogiczne podejście do problemu ochrony zdrowia w krajowych i zagranicznych źródłach naukowych; oszczędzanie zdrowia zostało zinterpretowane jako zjawisko społeczno-kulturowe w systematycznej orientacji podmiotów procesu edukacyjnego w celu zapewnienia fizycznego, duchowego, psychicznego i społecznego dobrostanu jednostki; podnoszenie wartości własnego zdrowia i zdrowia innych; proces skoncentrowany na samoregulacji jednostki i nabyciu sensu zdrowego stylu życia; proces edukacji i wychowania, który nie szkodzi bezpośrednio ani pośrednio zdrowiu, tworzy bezpieczne i wygodne środowisko, zapewnia dziecku trajektorię edukacyjną z zapobieganiem stresowi i przeciążeniu.

Na podstawie analizy porównawczej rozróżnia się podstawowe definicje pojęć dotyczących konstrukcji pedagogicznej stwierdzonego problemu w zagranicznych źródłach naukowych i pedagogicznych: „promocja zdrowia” jest interpretowana jako proces kształtowania zdrowego stylu życia, odpowiedzialnego zachowania za zdrowie i zdrowie innych; jako rzecznicstwo, promocja zdrowego stylu życia, która ma na celu promowanie polityki zdrowotnej, tworzenie środowiska przyjaznego dla zdrowia, rozwijanie partnerstw, umiejętności osobistych i zwiększanie dostępności usług opieki zdrowotnej.

Przeprowadzona kategoriowa analiza wyodrębnionych pojęć pozwoliła ustalić ich obecność w teorii i praktyce pedagogicznej, gdzie stanowią one istotę procesów przyczyniających się do wzmocnienia, formacji, zdrowia jednostki.

Podkreślono priorytet oszczędzania zdrowia w kształtowaniu i rozwoju osobowości; podkreślił znaczenie harmonizacji przestrzeni kulturowej i edukacyjnej.

Zdrowie narodu jest wskaźnikiem cywilizacji państwa, głównym kryterium skuteczności jego rozwoju społecznego, własnością zarówno jednostki, jak i całego społeczeństwa. Aktywność życiowa każdej osoby zależy w dużej mierze od jej stanu zdrowia, a zatem pomyślny rozwój społeczeństwa zależy od zdrowia całej populacji. Niewątpliwie ludzkie zdrowie to nie tylko brak chorób, ale także dobre samopoczucie, energia, radość, zdolność szybkiego powrotu do zdrowia po przeciążeniu i skuteczne przezwyciężenie chorób. Zdrowie determinuje duchowe, społeczno-ekonomiczne i ludzko-biologiczne dobro społeczeństwa, poziom cywilizacji kraju.

Promowanie i ochrona zdrowia jest wartością o strategicznym znaczeniu dla pomyślnego rozwoju społeczeństwa, zasobem i celem życia każdego człowieka, a zatem należy do bieżących zadań edukacyjnych. Humanizacja edukacji wymaga nowego jakościowo podejścia do ludzkich potrzeb, tworzenia trwałych motywacji do zdrowego stylu życia, pozytywnych zachowań społecznych i pielęgnowania kultury ochrony zdrowia w ogóle.

Słowa kluczowe: zdrowie, ochrona zdrowia, kultura zdrowia, zdrowy styl życia, promocja zdrowia.

SOCIO-CULTURAL PHENOMENON OF HEALTHCARE AND ITS PLACE IN THE SYSTEM OF PEDAGOGICAL CATEGORIES

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Abstract. On the basis of analysis and generalization of a number of scientific researches the author substantiates the urgency of the problem raised, made a theoretical excursion into its essence; stressed that health is a socio-cultural phenomenon; the essential characteristics of the basic definitions, their genesis, ways of formation in the aspect of the specified direction and their place in the system of pedagogical categories as an important concept of the concept of education, dynamic, holistic formation, manifested at different levels of life: somatic, mental, moral, spiritual.

There are a number of concepts that define the essential basis of the study, including "health", "health saving", "culture of health saving", "health promotion" ("healthpromotion"); basic aspects of health care have been analysed.

It is stated that the semantic characteristics of basic concepts of the problem of health saving are successfully introduced into the system of pedagogical categories; analysed concepts are widely used in pedagogical theory and practice, representing the essence of the basic processes associated with the preservation, strengthening and formation of the phenomenon under study.

The scientific and pedagogical approaches to the problem of health protection in domestic and foreign scientific sources are characterized; health saving has been interpreted as a socio-cultural phenomenon in the systematic orientation of the subjects of the educational process to ensure the physical, spiritual, mental and social well-being of the individual; raising the value of one's own health and the health of others; a process focused on self-regulation of the individual and the acquisition of the meaning of a healthy lifestyle; a process of education and upbringing that does not directly or

indirectly harm health, creates a safe and comfortable environment, provides an educational trajectory for the child with the prevention of stress and overload.

On the basis of the comparative analysis the basic definitions of the concepts concerning the pedagogical construct of the stated problem in foreign scientific and pedagogical sources are distinguished: «healthpromotion» is interpreted as the process of forming a healthy lifestyle, responsible behaviour for one's health and the health of others; as advocacy, promotion of a healthy lifestyle, which is to promote health policies, create a health-friendly environment, develop partnerships, personal skills, and increase the availability of health care services.

Conducted categorical analysis of isolated concepts allowed to ascertain their presence in pedagogical theory and practice, where they represent the essence of processes that contribute to the strengthening, formation, health of the individual.

The priority of health saving in the formation and development of personality is emphasized; emphasized the importance of harmonizing the cultural and educational space.

The health of the nation is an indicator of the civilization of the state, the main criterion for the effectiveness of its social development, the property of both the individual and the entire society. Each person's life activity is largely determined by his or her state of health and, accordingly, the successful development of society depends on the health of the entire population. Undoubtedly, human health is not only a lack of disease, but also well-being, energy, cheerfulness, the ability to quickly recover from overloads and successfully overcome diseases. Health determines the spiritual, socio-economic and human-biological well-being of society, the level of civilization of the country.

Promoting and preserving health is a value that is of strategic importance for the successful development of society, a resource and a goal of life for every individual, and therefore belongs to current educational tasks. The humanization of education requires a qualitatively new approach to human needs, the formation of sustainable motivations for healthy lifestyles, positive social behaviour, and nurturing a culture of health conservation in general.

Key words: health, health preservation, the culture of health, healthy lifestyle, health promotion.

СОЦІОКУЛЬТУРНИЙ ФЕНОМЕН ЗДОРОВ'ЯЗБЕРЕЖЕННЯ ТА ЙОГО МІСЦЕ У СИСТЕМІ ПЕДАГОГІЧНИХ КАТЕГОРІЙ

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Анотація. На основі аналізу й узагальнення низки наукових досліджень автором обґрунтовано актуальність порушеної проблеми, зроблено теоретичний екскурс у її сутність; наголошено, що здоров'язбереження є соціокультурним феноменом; виокремлено сутнісні характеристики основних дефініцій, їх генезу, шляхи формування в аспекті зазначеного напрямку та їх місце в системі педагогічних категорій як важливе поняття концепції освіти, динамічне, цілісне

утворення, що виявляється на різних рівнях життєдіяльності: соматичному, психічному, моральному, духовному.

Охарактеризовано коло понять, що визначають сутнісну основу дослідження, серед яких «здоров'я», «здоров'язбереження», «культура здоров'язбереження», «сприяння здоров'ю» («healthpromotion»); здійснено аналіз основних аспектів здоров'язбереження.

Констатовано, що смислові характеристики базових понять проблеми здоров'язбереження успішно вводяться у систему педагогічних категорій; проаналізовані поняття широко використовуються у педагогічній теорії та практиці, репрезентуючи сутність основних процесів, пов'язаних зі збереженням, зміцненням і формуванням досліджуваного феномену.

Схарактеризовано науково-педагогічні підходи до проблеми здоров'язбереження у вітчизняних і зарубіжних наукових джерелах; по трактовано здоров'я збереження як соціокультурний феномен у системній спрямованості зусиль суб'єктів освітнього процесу на забезпечення фізичного, духовного, психічного й соціального благополуччя особистості; підвищення ціннісного ставлення до власного здоров'я та здоров'я оточуючих; процес, орієнтований на саморегуляцію особистості та надбання сенсу здорового способу життя; процес навчання й виховання, що прямо чи опосередковано не шкодить здоров'ю, створює безпечні й комфортні умови, забезпечує освітню траєкторію дитини із запобіганням стресів та перевантаження.

На основі порівняльного аналізу виокремлено основні визначення понять щодо педагогічного контакту заявленої проблеми в іноземних науково-педагогічних джерелах: «healthpromotion» По трактовано як процес формування здорового способу життя, відповідальної поведінки за своє здоров'я та здоров'я інших; як пропаганду, популяризацію здорового способу життя, що полягає в поширенні політики сприяння здоров'ю, створенні здоров'язбережувального середовища, розвитку партнерської взаємодії, особистісних навичок та підвищенні рівня доступності медичних послуг із охорони здоров'я.

Проведений категоріальний аналіз виокремлених понять дозволив констатувати їх присутність у педагогічній теорії і практиці, де вони представляють сутність процесів, що сприяють зміцненню, формуванню, здоров'язбереженню особистості.

Підкреслено пріоритетність здоров'язбереження у становленні та розвитку особистості; наголошено на важливості гармонізації культурно-освітнього простору особистості через здоров'язбережувальні технології.

Ключові слова: здоров'я, здоровий спосіб життя, сприяння здоров'ю, («healthpromotion»); культура, здоров'язбереження, культура здоров'язбереження.

Formulation of the problem in general and its relation to important scientific or practical tasks. Modern education in the field of health, safety and social integration is of great importance and is a priority for development. In 2014, UNESCO proclaimed eight key industries for the 21st century competencies, including physical and psychological well-being, social cohesion, as these are directly related to health, safety and social inclusion.

The updated Framework of Key Competences for Lifelong Learning has been endorsed by the European Parliament (2018), which includes competences for personal, social, educational and health, safety and social wellbeing.

These priorities are reflected in the National Standards for Elementary and General Secondary Education, defining mandatory education for health, physical education, social and health care; basic principles of the concept of "New Ukrainian School", providing for the formation of healthy lifestyles and creation of conditions for physical and psycho-emotional development, creating an atmosphere of trust and mutual respect, transforming the school into a safe place, etc. [Health Teaching Pedagogy at the New Ukrainian School].

An analysis of recent research and publications that have addressed aspects of the issue and based on the author's opinion; highlighting previously unresolved parts of a common problem. Human health is the greatest asset, as well as a complex, complex problem of modern science. It should be noted that the concept of "health" is widely used by domestic and foreign specialists in various fields, who apply their approaches in research in philosophy, pedagogy and sociology. Please note that there is no single approach to understanding this phenomenon, particularly in pedagogical research. The opinions of scientists are debatable and need a thorough and comprehensive study of this concept and its close in content.

Studies in Valeology (G. Apanasenko, Y. Boychuk, I. Brehman, E. Weiner, M. Goncharenko, V. Horaschuk, M. Grinova, V. Kulinichenko, S. Strashko, and S. Strashko) became relevant in the study of human health issues. etc.). Historical and pedagogical search in modern Ukrainian pedagogy testifies to the special role of a person in the formation of his own physical, mental and social health, as emphasized by domestic scientists (V. Kohan, V. Panok, T. Titarenko, etc.). Psychological and pedagogical bases of formation of healthy way of life of schoolboys, formation of health saving skills, abilities and competences of elementary school students are in the sphere of scientific interests O. Vashchenko, L. Vysochan, M. Dedlovskaya, B. Dolinsky and others; O. Dubogai, S. Dudko, V. Ilchenko, L. Slivka, and others used the use of health-saving technologies in primary school to promote the health of participants in educational interaction, and to create a health-saving educational environment. In the works of T. Berezhnaya, V. Orzhekhovskaya, attention is paid to the necessity of introducing health-saving education in general educational institutions, formation of a value attitude to health, reproduction and strengthening of one's own health and the health of others.

The concept of "culture of human health", as a pedagogical category, has been attached to many admirers by scholars L. Zaplatnikov, G. Maksimenko, T. Roters, G. Shevchenko and others. Various aspects of health, which were discovered, were described in the scientific work of V. Horashchuk, G. Krivosheeva (from the side of the health culture); O. Gasnitia, O. Ezhova (this is a valuable attitude to health); S. Sviridenko (a very healthy lifestyle). O. Kalyuzhnaya, V. Kuzmenko, D. Solopchuk and others are solitary emphasize the inaccuracy of the health of health, and in a comprehensive school. A holistic model of a multicomponent approach to health has been developed by a number of students (R. Aizman, B. Bratus, M. Goncharenko, I. Dubrovina, V. Kukushin) who have been used in production (physical, psycho-emotional, intellectual, responsible, personality and spiritual).

In foreign sources on the outlined problems, scientists pay special attention to the issues of physical and mental well-being of students, organization of training on the principles of health saving (A. Antonovsky, I. Blumberg, T. Brandon, E. Clausson, etc.); preparing teachers for health care activities (J. Murray, E. Downes, A. Wenger, etc.).

Formulation of the goals of the article (formulation of the task): to substantiate the relevance of the problem of health care as a socio-cultural phenomenon, its place in the

system of pedagogical categories, on the basis of analysis and generalization of scientific researches; to distinguish the essential characteristics of the basic definitions, "health", "health saving", "healthpromotion" and their semantic constructs, to characterize scientific and pedagogical approaches to the problem of health care in domestic and foreign scientific sources.

It should be noted that the problem of fostering a culture of health care in the educational process of the modern school is not sufficiently covered in the scientific literature. The research focuses mainly on the means of physical education in the conditions of school and out-of-school educational establishments, children's and youth sports schools.

To solve these problems, the following methods were used: analysis, synthesis, comparison, generalization of scientific literature on the problem of research in order to determine the state of its scientific development.

Outline of the main research material with full justification of scientific results.

In the pedagogical, sociological and philosophical works, the concept of "health" is investigated according to the subject and tasks. Let's find out the definitions of this concept and consider its pedagogical essence. There are about 450 definitions of human health, which can be attributed to six basic types: 1) health as a standard of life of the organism at all levels of its organization; 2) health as a harmonious state of vital functions of the body; 3) health as a manifestation of the full implementation of social functions, participation in public life and active work; 4) the ability to adapt to environmental conditions; 5) absence of diseases and normal state of health; 6) a state of complete physical, spiritual, mental and social well-being. At the same time, it should be noted that to date there is no generally accepted definition of the concept of "human health" (*Batyuk, 2013*).

"Health is a state of complete physical, spiritual and social well-being, not just the absence of disease and physical disabilities," - stated in the Statute of the World Health Organization (*WHO Charter*).

In the Encyclopaedia of Education, the definition of "health" is characterized as "a dynamic state of the organism, characterized by high energy potential, optimal adaptive responses to environmental changes, which ensures the harmonious physical, psycho-emotional and social development of the individual, his active longevity, complete life effective control of the disease" (*Encyclopaedia of education, 2008, p. 318*).

We consider worthy to state that "health is a holistic dynamic state characterized by certain reserves of synergistic, plastic and regulatory functions, resilience to negative environmental factors and is the basis for performing social and biological functions" (*The general theory of health and health: a collective monograph, Boychuk, 2017*).

Maintaining and promoting health is linked to the general human culture, which contains an important component - the culture of health. The term "culture" is seen as a set of socially acquired ideas, values, customs, traditions, norms of behaviour through which people organize their activities and pass them on from generation to generation. It envisages the pedagogical aspect as an opportunity to influence the formation of a culture of health, since human values (ethical, moral, aesthetic) are concentrated in it. They determine the way and style of life of the people, their ideological traditions, the basics of health-saving behaviour in society.

The term "culture of health" was introduced by the teacher V. Klimov in the late XX century as an important component of the general human culture, conditioned by

material and spiritual environment in the system of values. Undoubtedly, an important component of the general human culture is the culture of health. A person with a sufficient level of health culture is not only a "consumer" of their health, but also a "producer" because it constantly cares for its preservation and strengthening. According to V. Gorashchuk, the culture of personality health is an important component of its general culture, conditioned by the material and spiritual environment of society, which is expressed in the system of values, knowledge, needs, abilities and skills in forming, preserving and strengthening her health (*Gorashchuk, 2008, p. 184*).

We are impressed by the paradigm of health culture developed by K. Oglobin, which includes the following provisions: pre-emptive humanization aimed at the person and all spheres of his life activity, which affirms the values of human, universal cultural achievements and considers above all the life of people and their social relations; probabilistic socialization, which is to pay attention to the social aspects of development: social ecology, social infrastructure, etc.; noospheric greening, which involves the consideration of a human being inseparably linked to its habitat, living conditions (*Oglobin, 2009, p.76-81*).

With this approach, it is quite legitimate to conclude that health culture is an integral part of the overall personality culture, provides an adequate level of knowledge, skills, skills in the formation, preservation, reproduction and promotion of one's own health and is characterized by a high level of health behaviour culture of others.

Modern scientific thought connects the culture of health with the degree of perfection achieved in mastering the theory and practice of optimization of human life, aimed at the adequate realization of its genetic potential, strengthening and development of the reserve capacity of the organism and improving the environment with the biosocial environment, functions of the individual and the progress of mankind as a whole. That is, a culture of health is a component of the general culture of the individual and provides him with an adequate level of knowledge, skills, skills to form, preserve, reproduce and enhance his own health, and is characterized by a high level of environmental and environmental behaviour culture.

Pedagogical science connects health with a culture of health-saving, health-saving education and a healthy lifestyle. From birth, the child learns the basics of culture and forms a world outlook. Displays patterns of attitudes and behaviours within the family and society, and consciously selects the rules that are guided throughout life. Accordingly, the child observes examples of health preservation or destruction in everyday life. That is why it is so important that the lifestyle of others, their behaviours contribute to the preservation of health, to instill in the child the foundations of a culture of health care.

Health culture, as the sum of knowledge, skills, is axiologically linked to the notion of a healthy lifestyle, since the health of the individual is directly determined by his or her lifestyle. Healthy lifestyles are seen as an integral component of a basic personality culture that seeks to preserve and improve human health. In particular, V. Boychuk believes that her lifestyle will manifest itself in the lifestyle - including adaptation to environmental conditions, harmony of all functional systems, ability to perform social functions to the full (*Boychuk, 2017*).

Indicators of a healthy lifestyle are the possession of appropriate methods of balancing external and internal factors affecting health, his physical and mental state, conscious attitude to his own needs, the organization of a rational mode of life to ensure

the harmonious functioning and interaction of all organs and systems. A person who leads a healthy lifestyle is an active, biological and social being at the same time.

Culture of a healthy way of life, according to L. Sokolenko's studies, includes environmental literacy, expedient use of reserve possibilities of the organism, reasonable use of folk methods of treatment. The researcher sees a fundamentally new approach, in which the preservation and promotion of health occurs through awareness of the capabilities of their body. This concept implies the presence of knowledge about the norms and values of various aspects of health, differentiated approach to innovative methods of healing and treatment of diseases, widespread use of valeological knowledge in professional and pedagogical activities, the ability to self-management and self-correction. To the components of a healthy lifestyle generally accepted alternation of work and rest, rational nutrition, lack of bad habits, physical activity, observance of rules of personal hygiene, tempering and psychologist yen.

As a pedagogical phenomenon of the concept of "health" by scientists (O. Glebov, V. Yefimov, O. Kokorina, Y. Lukyanov) is considered in the systematic orientation of the subjects of the educational process to ensure the physical, spiritual, mental and social well-being of the child; a process that promotes the health of children in educational institutions, one of the means of improving the effectiveness of education, preserving health, aimed at transforming the intellectual and emotional spheres of the individual, enhancing the value of their own health and the health of others; a process focused on self-regulation of the individual and the acquisition of the meaning of a healthy lifestyle; a process of education and upbringing that does not directly or indirectly harm the health of children, creates safe and comfortable conditions, provides an educational trajectory for the child with the prevention of stress and overload (*Obukhovskaya, Tsushko, 2015*).

Summarizing the views of scientists in the interpretation of the above concepts, we can conclude that a healthy lifestyle - these are typical and essential for a given socio-economic formation species, types, ways of life that enhance the adaptive capacity of the human body, contribute to the successful recovery, maintenance and development of it backup capabilities, full human performance of social functions and the achievement of active longevity. A healthy lifestyle as an active activity of the subject is motivated by the motives that determine its orientation to preserve and enhance health. The integrity of human culture must be reproduced as a symbol in every human being. Accordingly, the system of interdependent "healthy-healthy lifestyle" cultural symbols must support the integrity of the culture through its reproduction in each individual. Health culture is a concept that is much broader than the concept of a healthy lifestyle, as it is an integral part of the general personality culture and is not only manifested in healthy personal life habits, but also becomes a criterion for evaluating one's lifestyle. The essence of the concept of "culture of health" is that a healthy lifestyle, as its main core - is scientifically sound, cultural, most rational and optimal in specific conditions, understood by the individual as a vital necessity, lifestyle. A key element in the "health-culture-health-healthy-lifestyle" triad is the value of health.

A specific form of co-ordinated activity of subjects who are and interact in the space of health is health-saving activity - a complex, multifunctional social phenomenon, which, in B. Dolinsky's belief, involves the introduction of health-saving methods by applying appropriate methods and methods educational process, which are aimed at the formation of health-saving skills and abilities, contribute to the preservation

of physical, mental, social, moral and spiritual health rov'ya participants in the educational process (*Dolinsky, 2010*).

According to A. Tsyplyuk, health-saving activity is a prerequisite for optimizing the social, mental and physical health of children through practical means of health-saving (selection and use of appropriate methods and forms in the educational process) (*Tsiplyuk, 2014*).

The analysis of foreign scientific literature has shown that there are a number of interrelated analogy concepts, including the term healthpromotion. The New Interpretative Dictionary of the Ukrainian Language explains that to contribute is to: 1) positively influence anything; create appropriate conditions for the implementation, implementation of anything; to assist in anything; be the cause or effect of the occurrence, existence of something; create, elicit a desire to perform any action; 2) indulge anyone. By definition, health promotion is refined with the provision of appropriate conditions for the formation, preservation and promotion of health and well-being of the individual (*Yaremenko, Slipushko, 1999, p.353*).

In Eastern European countries, the concept of "healthpromotion" is explained in accordance with the definition of the Ottawa Charter (WHO Programming Document) as a multifaceted social and political process that allows people to increase control over their health in order to preserve and promote it; covers not only actions aimed at developing skills, physical, mental and social capacities of the person, but also actions aimed at changing social, environmental and economic conditions, which allows to increase the effectiveness of their impact on the health of the population, society and the individual human. In the abbreviated version it is interpreted as promotion, promotion, advertising (*Ezhov, Besedin, Berezhna, 2016*).

The definition of healthpromotion is interpreted as the process of forming a healthy lifestyle, responsible behaviour for one's health and the health of others; such as advocacy, promotion of a healthy lifestyle, which is to promote health policies, create a health-friendly environment, develop partnerships, personal skills, and improve the availability of health care services. In particular, there are health promotion schools in Hungary, whose activities are aimed at providing health care, developing a system of primary disease prevention through strengthening the activities of local and regional health institutions responsible for maintaining and promoting the health of children and adolescents - preventive maintenance and support of students (*Solopchuk, Zaikin, 2006*).

Polish scientists refer to the term "healthpromotion" as a process aimed at shaping, preserving and promoting human health. Thus, T. Williams and B. Voynarovsk introduce the definition of "romocjздrowia", which means taking care of one's own health and the health of society as a whole, as well as awareness and identification of one's own health problems; identification of possibilities for their solution; decision-making to improve health; the art of adapting in society and encouraging people to create and develop a health-saving environment (*Solopchuk, Zaikin, 2006*).

A similar term is proposed by Czech scientist M. Gavlinov, namely "rodporuzdravi" - the positive influence of various factors and conditions on all aspects of human health (biological, psychological, spiritual and ecological) and on his lifestyle and behaviour. The identical Hungarian term "egészségfejlesztést" is interpreted as promoting healthy lifestyles, including the creation of a healthy environment, the development of personal skills, the primary prevention of diseases and education based on the formation of life skills (*Ezhov, Besedin, Berezhna, 2016*).

In O. Yezhova's monograph, the term "health promotion" is explained as a process of making efforts to promote the health and well-being of a person, forming a value attitude to health, realizing the value of health and creating the necessary conditions for engaging in a healthy way life that will contribute to the preservation and enhancement of the health and well-being of the individual (*Yezhov, 2011*).

WHO (World Health Organization) experts in the field of health promotion M. O'Donnell and L. Green offer their understanding of the concept under study. In particular, the former believes that health promotion is the art and science of combining lifestyle and optimal health by shaping a person's desire for optimal health, making changes in behaviour, lifestyle necessary to achieve optimal health. Optimal health is a dynamic balance of physical, emotional, social, spiritual and intellectual health. L. Green understands health promotion as promoting healthy lifestyles and combining health education and social support for those actions and conditions that promote health preservation and promotion (*Ezhov, Besedin, Berezhna, 2016*).

Analysing the interpretation of the concept of "health promotion" proposed by domestic and foreign scientists, it should be emphasized that they all define forms of health promotion and promotion, promote health as a value promote a healthy lifestyle. The differences are the means and ways of engaging a person in a healthy lifestyle. It is impossible to take care of one's own and public health without knowing why. The wider and more thorough the education of the individual as a whole, the deeper his or her perception of health is. The starting point in pedagogy is a comprehensive understanding of education in the provision of information, learning methods, techniques and skills of health care, education and awareness of the priority of health values of the individual and the public.

Research findings and prospects for further exploration of this area.

The analysis of the scientific literature concerning the problems of promoting the health of the younger generation suggests that the above-mentioned concepts accumulate in their content assessments, actions, ways of organizing activities aimed at forming an understanding of the essence of health as an undeniable value of man and society. The term "health" is the core of other concepts. The multidimensionality of related definitions allows us to consider this phenomenon from the standpoint of interdisciplinary scientific knowledge, which includes qualitatively different components and reflects fundamental aspects of human being - physical, spiritual, social.

Thus, it is quite legitimate to state that health is one of the most important indicators of the "quality" of a person and society. In various approaches to the definition of "health", scientists are unanimous that one of the hallmarks of this state is the harmonious unity of biological and social qualities, caused by the interaction of genotype and environment, that is, health is always an individual way of life, which corresponds to the psychophysical constitution of man and his behaviour.

The prospects for further scientific exploration are linked to the study of the future teacher's readiness to educate young people's health culture.

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